

SciencesPo

TIERED PROJECT
Student Works Collection

Special AI Issue

SPRING 2025

CAN AI BENEFIT DEMOCRACY ?

*Articles from the transdisciplinary
student conference*

FRANCE

2025

CONTENTS

4 FOREWORD

5 EDITORIAL

PART 1

7 HOW TO REGULATE AI ? Introduction

8 From Scarcity to Scale: Cross-Border Data Flows for Artificial Intelligence

11 Will Trespassers Be Prosecuted? A Review of Privacy Rights in the Age of AI

13 The New Information Economy: Fair Training and Copyright in the EU

PART 2

15 AI FOR GREATER (IN)EQUALITY ? - Introduction

16 Deploying AI for Energy Access

19 AI and Disability

21 Complex biases in generative AI: Exploring Religious Bias in Stable Diffusion

PART 3

26 CITIZENS AND AI : A QUESTION OF TRUST ? - Introduction

27 Building Accountability : Transparency, Explainability and Appeal Processes: The Case of AMS Austria

30 Ensuring the Right Effective Remedies in Welfare ADM: The case of the Dutch SyRI

33 Understanding Public Opinion on AI in Policy-Making Using Pol.is

35 BIBLIOGRAPHY

FOREWORD

Digital and environmental transformations are reshaping our democracies, and Sciences Po is committed to preparing students to tackle these complex challenges.

Sciences Po courses combine theoretical learning with practical case studies and give our students the tools to develop high-quality insights and policy recommendations. In doing so, students build off the human and social science research, which anchors their educational paths, to contribute meaningfully to public debate.

To share these outcomes, this year Sciences Po has launched a **new Collection**, featuring works by students from various bachelor and master programs. Several Sciences Po Schools have already published issues based on collective student projects.

This special issue on Artificial Intelligence draws from multiple master's programs and builds on the **Sciences Po Student Conference, "Can AI benefit democracy?"**, held on 21 February 2025. Despite different disciplinary backgrounds, student perspectives converged around three core themes — **regulation, inequality, and citizenship & trust** — echoing topics from the **Intergovernmental AI Action Summit** held earlier that month in Paris. The quality of the discussions made the conference a powerful space for a nuanced and in-depth democratic debate. Students from the Sciences Po **School of Public Affairs, Law School, School of International Affairs, and School of Management and Impact** participated in the three roundtables, supported by their program directors.

The event attracted a full house, with students and audience members embracing the high-level discussions. Sharing this work more widely, including with AI Summit organisers, aligns with Sciences Po's mission: in the age of artificial intelligence, democracy still relies on a collective intelligence capable of generating and exchanging ideas for action.

The conference and the collection were created in the framework of the **TIERED project** - Transforming Interdisciplinary Education and Research for Evolving Democracies. At the heart of Sciences Po's institutional strategy, TIERED addresses the pressures on democratic systems from the environmental and digital evolutions. To understand the latter, it created the **Open Institute for Digital Transformations**, which provided the needed scientific oversight for this issue and the conference.

Congratulations to the students for their excellent work and happy reading!

Amélie Antoine Audo
TIERED Deputy Director
Associate Vice President for Studies and Partnerships
Sciences Po

EDITORIAL

As **artificial intelligence transforms** our institutions, economies, and daily lives, governing its impact demands **the insights and expertise of the social sciences**. AI might seem like a purely technical field, but it is built on social data and touches every aspect of society. Technical innovation alone cannot safeguard democracy or ensure justice. It is through ethical reflection, legal scrutiny, and social inquiry that we can turn AI into a true public interest technology. **This series of research projects by Sciences Po students highlights the vital role that social sciences can play in evaluating and guiding the integration of AI into democratic societies.**

The collection is organized in three parts, reflecting both the scope of the challenge and the richness of research from different training programs. **Each part addresses a central issue in the AI and democracy debate:** the need for **effective and fair regulation** in a world of global data flows and changing legal frameworks; the **potential of AI to either reduce or worsen inequality** in different social contexts; and the fundamental question of **public trust**, with a focus on transparency, accountability, and citizen participation in AI governance. Together, these essays show that **the future of democracy** depends not only on technology but also on rigorous and principled inquiry, which the social sciences can uniquely provide.

We invite readers to consider that **a democratic future for AI is neither guaranteed nor impossible**—it must be **deliberately imagined and built**. The **Open Institute for Digital Transformations** at Sciences Po calls for a shared effort by legal scholars, sociologists, political scientists, and economists to help shape this future. This is **a collective challenge** that welcomes everyone: researchers, engineers, teachers, and, perhaps most importantly, students, who will be most directly affected by the choices we make today.

Jean-Philippe Cointet
Director of the Open Institute for Digital Transformations
Sociology Professor at médialab
Sciences Po

“This conference was a refreshing gathering of young professionals and students, offering sharp and insightful identification of contemporary AI policy issues. I thoroughly enjoyed witnessing the diverse range of AI policy challenges presented without agendas, driven purely by genuine interest, academic enthusiasm and delivered by uniquely knowledgeable individuals.”

~ Stavroula Chousou, student and speaker

Student Conference: “Can AI Benefit Democracy ?”
21 February 2025 - Moderated by:

- **Saurabh Mishra**, Co-Founder and CEO of Taiyō.AI, teacher at Sciences Po Urban School
- **Valérie Peugeot**, Director of the Digital Humanities Executive Master, and Scientific Advisor of the School of Public Affairs' Digital, New Technology and Public Policy policy stream at Sciences Po

Part 1

HOW TO REGULATE AI ?

Unlike physical trade, AI relies on intangible flows—data, models, computing power, software. These cross borders invisibly but are increasingly contested. As of 2025, data localization laws and compute sovereignty are reshaping digital trade, particularly among the US, EU, and China. Yet most multilateral institutions are not equipped to regulate this emerging form of AI-based “invisible trade.”

Governments are investing heavily in AI to boost productivity and geopolitical standing, even as labor markets face rising uncertainty and skill mismatches. In a world of aging populations and skill shortages, we must move past binary narratives of AI-as-threat versus AI-as-savior, and instead govern AI as part of a dynamic labor and innovation system.

From Scarcity to Scale: Cross-Border Data Flows for Artificial Intelligence

Gustavo Ribeiro, Luisa Veronica Arroyo Revatta, Karin Hess
 This article is based on work prepared at the Sciences Po School of Public Affairs (EAP)

INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly digital world, data has become a strategic asset for businesses, governments and organizations. Firms are progressively relying on data to improve their operations, gain more efficiency and enhance user experience (The Economist, 2017), while governments are also striving to create public value through data-driven public policies (OECD, 2019; OECD, 2014). Global value chains, in which processes are fragmented, are also being transformed by data. Not only goods and services flow within these global production chains, but data is also inevitably exchanged. As Casalini et al. (2021) stress, “it is increasingly difficult for an international trade transaction to take place without a cross-border data transfer of some sort” (p.6).

As such, cross border data flows, understood as the “movement or transfer of information between computer servers across national borders” (Fefer, 2020, p.3), are vital for organizations, both for their internal business and for their interactions with suppliers and customers. In the 2020s, the value of data gained a new dimension. Data became the indispensable “raw material” of artificial intelligence (AI), fundamental to training, deploying and continuously improving AI systems.

Against this background, this text addresses how cross-border data flows may support the scientific progress of AI. Alongside this, it responds to the following questions:

How does cross-border data flow and its governance support AI scientific progress? How are countries regulating these flows? Where do they diverge and converge? What convergencies in data governance can be explored to advance data flows across borders and consequently AI?

UNDERSTANDING CROSS-BORDER DATA FLOW

Kaplan et al. (2020) show that both data quantity and quality lead to improved AI capabilities. Cross-border flows can advance access to data in larger quantity and of better quality for several reasons explored below.

Figure 1 (Villalobos et al., 2024).

Firstly, the stock of available training data is finite, and frontier AI systems are quickly approaching that limit. For example, Villalobos et al. (2024) put forward evidence on the scarcity of human generated text data to train language models. The authors show that, between 2026 and 2032, the size of datasets used to train frontier LLMs is projected to be equal to that of all available human generated text data stock (Figure 1).

Secondly, cross-border data flows can improve the quality of training data by diversifying data provenance. As explained by Longpre et al. (2024), “diversity and representation in training datasets, and among their creators, are widely acknowledged as essential to building AI models that are less biased, more useful, and more equitable” (p.7). They show there is an inequality gap in the geographic sources of multimodal AI training data, with little data coming from Africa and South America relative to the rest of the world (Figure 2).

	AFRICA	ASIA	EUROPE	N AMERICA	OCEANIA	S AMERICA
<i>By Count</i>						
TEXT	0.3	13.4	24.0	61.5	0.7	0.2
SPEECH	3.6	35.7	30.4	30.4	0.0	0.0
VIDEO	0.0	25.2	24.4	48.0	0.8	1.6
<i>By Tokens or Hours</i>						
TEXT	0.0	6.1	55.4	38.4	0.1	0.0
SPEECH	0.1	38.8	18.8	42.4	0.0	0.0
VIDEO	0.0	23.1	22.0	38.2	16.7	0.1

Figure 2 (Longpre et al., 2024)

In conclusion, cross-border data flows have the potential to improve both the quantity and quality of data. First, because the transfer of information across national borders allows for individuals and firms within a given country to have access to data generated in other countries, as seen in Figure 2. Second, because this data is representative of a variety of characteristics due to its plurality of sources, which in turn improves dataset quality.

THE GOVERNANCE OF CROSS-BORDER DATA FLOW

With this established, **governance becomes central in enabling or hindering cross-border flows.** Depending on policy goals across types of data (e.g., national security data, personal data), countries have developed different regulatory approaches to cross-border flows that may be categorized across a spectrum from leniency and restrictiveness in four ways (Figure 3).

Figure 3 (prepared by the authors based on Casalini et al., 2021)

On the lenient end, some countries have no regulation on data transfers: data can be sent abroad without restriction. Others impose ex-post accountability measures on the data exporter “if data sent abroad is misused.” **Conditioning flows is a stricter approach that relies on safeguards**, including “a range of preauthorized and transparent conditions for data transfer.” Conditions vary, but often refer to equal levels of data protection in the country to where data is transferred. Governments can issue an “adequacy decision” recognizing other countries as offering such equal level of protection and, thus, allowing for data to freely flow between them. Absent that, other instruments may authorize international transfers, such as standard contractual clauses (Casalini et al., 2021, p.9). Finally, restrictive countries only allow transfers with ad-hoc authorizations on a case-by-case basis. They may also outrightly prohibit it by requiring data localization; that is, data can only be processed and stored locally.

The three major economic blocs—China, the EU, and the US—exert outsized influence over global data governance. Their market size and regulatory reach often compel other countries to align with their rules in order to access these digital economies. China follows an approach of ad hoc approach authorization for data that may expose national security interests (e.g., “important data”). Still, alongside the EU, China adheres to conditional

flows for personal data. In the US, this is not the case at the federal level, but more common at state level; among which the most influential is the State of California (NYT, 2021).

Overall, China, EU, and US diverge on the governance of cross border flows in the areas of national security and personal data protection, whereby regulatory barriers to data flows persist. Yet, all of them converge in the belief that data flows are a medium to digital trade which, in turn, advances economic development and welfare (Figure 4). Missing from this picture is the information exchange that comes with cross-border data flows, which leads to larger data pools of higher quality, and thus advances the scientific progress of artificial intelligence.

Figure 4 (Prepared by the authors)

The governance approaches adopted by China, EU and US are foundational to global convergence since they command the biggest markets in the world (Ma, 2024). Although they are unaligned on data governance, there are overlaps in the conditions they impose for data flows (Figure 5).

Instruments enabling data flow	GDPR (2016)	CCPA (2018)	PIPL (2021), DSL (2021)
Adequacy Decision	Art. 45	NA	NA
Standard Contractual Clauses (SCC)	Art. 46(2)(f), Art. 46(3)(a), Art. 93(2)	Sec. 1789.100(d)	Art. 38(3), PIPL
Certification Mechanism	Art. 46(2)(f), Art. 42, Art. 43	NA	Art. 38(2), PIPL
Binding Corporate Rules	Art. 46(2)(b), Art. 47	NA	NA
Code of Conduct	Art. 46(2)(e), Art. 40, Art. 42	NA	NA
Security Assessment Measures	NA	NA	Art. 31, DLS; Art. 40, PIPL

Figure 5 (Prepared by the authors)

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on these commonalities, there are three set of measures any country wishing to foster cross border data flows as a medium for digital trade and the scientific progress of AI can explore: They can leverage, understand and expand shared mechanisms for international data transfer.

First, they should leverage overlapping conditions that authorize data transfers. For example, among the major economic blocs, standard contractual clauses are the only commonly shared instrument,

whereas China and the EU also rely on certification mechanisms for transfers of personal data.

With enough alignment, these instruments could reduce fragmentation and regulatory costs for data transfers. Yet, while these tools share a common purpose, their operational details often diverge. For instance, China, the EU, and the US may each require a standardized contract for data exports, but the content of those contracts varies across jurisdictions. This leads us to the next recommendation.

Second, countries need to **understand** how these mechanisms function in practice. **A global repository of data governance frameworks would allow governments to identify overlaps and gaps across systems.** This would create a foundation for gradually developing shared specifications. In the case of contractual clauses, convergence on common terms would allow data exporters to use a single agreement for multiple destinations. Similarly, a harmonized certification process between China and the EU would provide streamlined access to both markets through one approval pathway.

Third, countries—especially those outside of the major economic blocs—can **expand** these shared governance mechanisms through establishing standardized data-sharing frameworks at the multilateral level. In the absence of progress, countries could embed them into digital chapters of free trade agreements, fostering alignment around common principles. These arrangements would reduce friction, promote trust, and allow data to circulate more freely, while respecting domestic policy concerns.

Taken together, these measures would enable cross-border data flows, broadening access to data essential for scientific advances in artificial intelligence. ■

Will Trespassers Be Prosecuted?

A Review of Privacy Rights in the Age of AI

Shefali Mehra

This article is based on work prepared at the Sciences Po School of Public Affairs (EAP)

INTRODUCTION

The article critically examines the evolving landscape of privacy rights amid the rise of digital technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI). The issue is framed not merely as regulatory or legal, but as civilizational and philosophical. AI technologies blur boundaries between public and private, individual and system, intention and inference. Consent, once a cornerstone of data protection, is now routinely undermined by dark patterns, datafication, and inference-based profiling. Historically, the idea of privacy emerged through different trajectories. Ancient Greek philosophy, notably Aristotle, distinguished between the *oikos* (household/private) and *polis* (public). Roman legal innovations offered mechanisms to redress personal intrusions, and this legacy continues in the “home as castle” principle. In the modern era, the landmark 1890 essay by Warren and Brandeis redefined privacy as “the right to be let alone.” Post-WWII international declarations like the UDHR and ICCPR positioned privacy as a universal human right. However, these definitions struggle to contain the vast implications of AI. Privacy is not a static right but a moving target shaped by social, technical, and political forces. The proliferation of AI exacerbates existing tensions—between state surveillance and autonomy, economic power and personal control, and between individuals and systemic inference engines. The stakes are further heightened in the Global South, where infrastructural and literacy divides render privacy notices illegible and consent mechanisms coercive.

METHODOLOGY

The investigation adopts a multidisciplinary method across four dimensions:

1. Philosophical analysis: Diverse intellectual traditions are used to examine what privacy means and why it matters. These include liberal theories of autonomy (Locke), utilitarianism’s cost-benefit logic (Bentham), Foucauldian critiques of surveillance and internalized discipline, and Marxist accounts of privacy as collective resistance to commodification. Special attention is given to Leonhard Menges’ “Deep Self View,” which links privacy to the moral integrity of a person’s stable values

2. Legal analysis: This dimension analyzes privacy laws across jurisdictions. The GDPR serves as a reference point, especially for its emphasis on consent,

purpose limitation, and data minimization. It also references international norms.

3. Technical analysis: These include the erosion of purpose limitation, expansion of secondary data uses, and the opacity of algorithmic decision-making. It highlights how AI challenges legal distinctions between personal and non-personal data through inference, and how Privacy-Enhancing Technologies (PETs) like differential privacy and federated learning aim to mitigate harms.

4. Empirical user study: A small-scale user study was conducted. It evaluates engagement with two privacy notices: a standard (Version A) and an enhanced version (Version B). Participants assessed clarity, opt-out visibility, and trust. Demographically based in India, the sample included users familiar with privacy norms but fatigued by digital consent experiences.

The method integrates normative critique, comparative legal research and technical risk mapping to triangulate, and empirical observation to arrive at a holistic understanding of privacy rights in AI contexts.

RESULTS

Across all dimensions, a common conclusion emerges: consent-based privacy frameworks are insufficient for the opaque, inferential, and behavioral nature of AI data processing:

1. Philosophical analysis reveals that privacy cannot be reduced to data ownership or control.

2. Legally, consent-based models are poorly equipped to regulate inferred or secondary uses of data.

3. Technically, AI undermines core data protection principles. Purpose limitation is diluted when AI repurposes data across domains. AI systems generate high-stakes inferences from seemingly innocuous data, eroding user control even in anonymized environments.

4. Empirically, the user study confirms the persistence of the privacy paradox. Despite familiarity with privacy laws, users often skip reading notices due to fatigue, complexity, or coercive designs. In Version A, 81.8% could not find a clear opt-out option. In Version B,

63.6% stated they would not have accepted in a real scenario, but 72.7% still found the decline option unclear. Design changes improve comprehension but do not fully overcome systemic challenges. The study also revealed qualitative concerns: users preferred visual cues, plain language, and modular options. Some trusted large firms by default.

The implications for the Global South are significant. Limited connectivity, lower digital literacy, and reliance on mobile devices intensify the gap between privacy as a right and as a lived reality.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Privacy in AI societies must be reimagined not as the individual’s burden to manage, but as a collective value requiring structural, technical, and ethical realignment. It is not just about data, but about power, dignity, and justice in a digitized world.

Privacy must be treated as a dignity-based right grounded in moral personhood, not just informational control. Normative theories like the Deep Self View offer inclusive frameworks that accommodate vulnerable populations.

Redesigning of privacy notices to include layered structures, visual cues, granular settings, and transparency dashboards is a technical imperative and using PETs like differential privacy, federated learning, and encryption could minimize data exposure by design. There is a need to shift from user-centric to structural safeguards, create international privacy task forces with regulators, technologists, and civil society to monitor AI impacts, and leverage Track 1.5 and South-South coalitions to establish equity-driven frameworks.

APPENDIX - SURVEY

A short survey was administered to assess how users engage with different privacy notice designs. Participants viewed two real-world privacy notices. After viewing each notice, participants completed a brief quiz assessing their understanding of the data practices described.

These results support existing literature that emphasizes the importance of clear, user-centric privacy designs in enabling informed consent and meaningful digital autonomy.■

Version A

Version B

The New Information Economy: Fair Training and Copyright in the EU

Marcus Woodcock

This article is based on work prepared at the Sciences Po Law School (EDD)

AI training in the EU operates within a legal framework that theoretically allows rightsholders to control their content and monitor its usage for AI training, notably through the Digital Single Market Directive and the AI Act. Though these set guidelines for data usage and transparency, enforcement challenges persist due to regulatory loopholes and evolving technological standards. **This article explores key regulatory gaps and proposes policy solutions for fair and effective AI governance.**

THE EUROPEAN COPYRIGHT MODEL

It is important to emphasise that there is no statutory right to remuneration for rightsholders provided for under EU law in the context of AI training. Instead, the EU regulatory mechanism establishes copyright exceptions focusing on practices of Text Data Mining (or TDM) in addition to transparency obligations for AI model providers.

Firstly, the framework provides control over rightsholders' content through the Digital Single Market Directive (CDSM – Directive 2019/790). The Digital Single Market Directive allows content creators to maintain control over their work through two key mechanisms outlined in Article 3 and Article 4. Article 3 allows specific institutions, such as research organizations and cultural heritage institutions, to mine data for research purposes without requiring explicit permission from content owners. Article 4 extends this possibility for commercial usage by allowing text and data mining, provided that the rightsholder has not opted out in a clear and machine-readable format, or via 'appropriate means'. If no opt-out is expressed, content can be used for mining.

Secondly, the AI Act complements the CDSM Directive by introducing additional transparency requirements. Specifically, Article 53(1) of the AI Act mandates that providers of general-purpose AI models must document the data used to train their models and make this information available to AI system providers who intend to integrate these models. **By requiring these disclosures, the AI Act ensures transparency in how AI systems are trained and what data is used in the process. This regulatory framework helps stakeholders, such as content creators, businesses and consumers, understand how AI models are developed and the data on which they are based.**

THE ISSUE WITH THE EU MODEL

Multiple issues hinder the effectiveness of these dual mechanisms, which are supposed to complement one another for the information economy to work efficiently.

a) Lack of common standards

In the absence of clear guidelines, defining the 'state of the art' regarding the implementation of opt-out provisions gives rise to certain ambiguities. One liberal interpretation of the opt-out option involves general opt-outs expressed by rightsholder associations, but these have limited practical effect since they aren't directly accessible to scraping services. Another approach uses natural language in websites' Terms and Conditions (T&Cs), but the complexity and variety of T&Cs across websites make this method challenging for AI companies to implement effectively. The robots.txt file, or robot exclusion protocol (REP), is another tool that allows website owners to control access to their content by specifying which bots can access certain parts of their site. However, the REP is limited in that it cannot express complex policies – such as object oriented or user-oriented authorisations - beyond 'allow/disallow'. Other protocols allowing for such options, however, fail to be adopted in a widespread manner.

b) Lack of enforceability

Additionally, the transparency obligations laid out by the AI Act, which are set to be established by the EU AI Office, are of limited efficacy. The template which has been drawn up by the AI Office is set to require the disclosure of a list of the top 10% of all internet domain names per type of data modality (modality being understood as the type of data, i.e. text, image etc...). **Therefore, the AI Office template summary, at best, allows rightsholders to assess the likelihood that their works were used to train a specific AI model.**

Moreover, there is presently an increasing decoupling of what is referred to as reasoning and information gathering for AI models. Increasingly, content is extracted through real-time web search by AI agents (such as Perplexity AI) which can perform searches to provide the most up-

to-date answers. Agentic AI systems are characterized by the ability to autonomously take actions which contribute towards achieving goals over an extended period. They are predicted to play an increasingly significant role in information extraction, processing and usage. **There is currently no framework for monitoring their actions, as they do not technically enter the field of training and are therefore not included within the remit of the transparency obligations under the AI act.** As a result of the inefficacy of opt-outs, technical protection measures (TPMs) - such as IP blocking and encryption - are used to protect content from scraping. This is complemented by the rise in use of data poisoning - methods which consist in formatting data so as to corrupt the AI system upon training. Both these methods are indiscriminate and prevent actors benefiting from Article 3 exceptions to conduct data-scraping. **Data poisoning in particular has an uncertain status under law and exacerbates uncertainty in the context of AI training.**

c) Complex interactions with other legal provisions

Additionally, though European law generally considers that data cannot be protected under copyright under the form of *mere facts*, the sui generis database right, provided in the Directive on the legal protection of databases, protects certain online databases. The criteria upon which the copyrightability of a database is posited is the level of 'investment made into the database', both financially and in terms of effort. However, it is not immediately evident to the trainer which databases are protected by sui generis rights, and which are not. **This threshold is far from transparent to the outside observer, and could hinder training practices, by exposing trainers who comply with opt-outs to additional legal uncertainty.**

d) Unequal bargaining power

There is currently no clear bargaining mechanism or framework for rightsholders to negotiate remuneration for their content. This is due to the multiplicity of rights holders which renders them uncoordinated and limits their bargaining power. Moreover, there is no transparent pricing mechanism for training content, which allows AI actors to unilaterally set the terms of agreements.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Ensure more granular conditions for opting out:

- Study other opt-out protocols, which allow more granular policy choices than *allow/disallow*, including automated remuneration and object- and actor-oriented access. This is particularly important in the growing context of agentic search.

2. Clarify additional regulation:

- **Clarify the application of sui generis databases regarding AI crawling:** sui generis copyright for databases, especially in the context of AI agents, may prove to be unmanageable in the context of AI agents and automated content extraction. Opt-out clauses could prove to be sufficient and provide legal certainty for the AI provider.
- **Clarify the legal status of data poisoning and Technical Protection Measures:** clarify the sanctions incurred for protecting non-copyrighted content and determine whether data poisoning is legal conduct.

3. Ensure traceability of AI agents:

- Ensure that AI agents are coded to be legally compliant, in particular regarding optouts, and that their actions are intelligible, traceable and auditable for right-holders, relevant authorities and users.

4. Establish a negotiation framework based on competition authorities:

- Establish a framework akin to the neighbouring rights negotiation mechanism established in the CDSM directive, which redresses inherent power imbalances between major AI actors and right holders, ensuring that AI actors negotiate in good faith, based on transparent, objective and non-discriminatory criteria, and ensure pricing transparency so that right holders may assess their remuneration for related rights. ■

Part 2

AI FOR GREATER (IN)EQUALITY ?

Artificial Intelligence presents both a risk and an opportunity in the fight against inequality. In developing countries, AI can help overcome persistent policy and implementation challenges that hinder access to essential services like energy. For instance, the underperformance of clean cooking initiatives—crucial for health and sustainability—can be addressed by using AI not as a replacement for human judgment but as a tool to support better policy execution and extend the longevity of development projects. In this context, AI has the potential to correct structural inequalities by enhancing the effectiveness of public action. However, in other areas, AI risks deepening exclusion. For people with disabilities, while 65% see technology as a source of opportunity, only 28% feel the same about AI, reflecting skepticism rooted in limited and often stereotypical representations. Tools exist that intend to depict disability narrowly, frequently defaulting to images of wheelchair users, thus overlooking the broad spectrum of physical, cognitive, and sensory conditions. This bias stems from the way AI is designed—by humans whose perceptions shape the outputs. A similar problem arises with religious representation in generative AI. Research from 2022 highlights how AI image-generation tools frequently marginalize or misrepresent religious practices, reflecting a lack of diversity in training data and design frameworks.

Through these three examples, we explore how AI systems, if not critically examined, can reproduce societal blind spots. Yet, with thoughtful governance and inclusive design, AI can also serve as a powerful tool for equity, amplifying underrepresented voices and correcting long-standing disparities. This is a both challenging and necessary issue for democratic societies.

Deploying AI for Energy Access

Clara Klint

*Based on her work with Isha Hiremath, Romain Cabanes, Wenxi Jiang, Ramiz Huseynzada
This article is based on work prepared at the Sciences Po Paris School of International Affairs
(PSIA)*

This project was originally developed for the Student AI & Energy Fair organised at the International Energy Organisation in December 2024, where our group of students of Sciences Po Paris School of International Affairs (Master in International Energy Transitions) pitched the Biogas Buddy App, an idea for improving energy access in emerging and developing economies using AI.

INTRODUCTION

AI solutions in the energy sector have predominantly focused on technical optimisation through top-down approaches. For example, several recent projects are developing AI to optimise the location of renewables or grids, and these kinds of applications tend to dominate the AI industry discourse. **This article challenges the traditional, technology-centric focus of AI applications, arguing that this narrow scope overlooks opportunities for innovative problem-solving across a broader spectrum of issues.**

Going beyond infrastructure and efficiency, this article explores how AI can address persistent policy and implementation challenges. **By applying AI to a complex issue in energy for development - the poor performance of clean cooking initiatives - we show that AI can be reframed as a tool to improve human policy execution and extend project life span.** In this way, the project illustrates how AI can support a more inclusive and resilient energy transition.

THE CLEAN COOKING ACCESS PROBLEM

Gathering biomass to cook over open fire without proper ventilation causes over 3.2 million premature deaths annually and is a stubborn barrier to women's economic development (WHO, 2024). Across decades, many solutions have been proposed to close the clean cooking gap, but despite ambitious projects and research, the problem of clean cooking remains pervasive. In some villages, 'graveyards' of disused cookstoves using different technologies from decades of failed clean cooking projects line kitchens (ECPA, 2022). It is shocking and outrageous that **there are still more than two billion people lacking**

access to clean cooking today, as progress struggles to keep pace with population growth (IEA, n.d).

One technology in particular, small biogas digesters, have been held up as a great promise in the fight for clean cooking. Since the 1980s, small biogas digesters have been promoted as a key solution to give more people clean cooking options, especially for remote villages, as biogas can be produced with locally available low-cost biomass. In theory, a biogas digester is a simple system, where the user feeds biomass and water into a dome and can obtain biogas through a pipe connected to a cookstove. Delving deep into the literature, it is apparent that many biodigesters projects fail. Research has shown that, within a few years of deployment, many biogas units fall into disrepair and are abandoned (see for example Chen et al, 2009; Hewitt et al, 2022; Roubik et al, 2016; Uwamahoro, 2021). With ambitious programmes like the Africa Biogas Partnership Program, which deployed 27,000 units in Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda between 2009-2013, there is an urgent need to understand the causes behind abandonment (Clemens et al, 2018)

The disconnect between a seemingly very suitable and accessible technology and its consistently weak performance puzzled our project group. **We wanted to understand what underlying trends cause these projects to fail and whether AI techniques could help bridge this gap.**

MAPPING PROJECT FAILURE

We set out to map the mechanisms which cause biogas projects to fail. The team delved into the literature on biogas projects for clean cooking, and mapped the insights from project evaluations, interview studies and other reports available. Most evidence seemed to point to predictable problems, such as poor feeding and maintenance habits, inadequate troubleshooting and difficulties in securing repairs as the root causes of failure (Hewitt et al, 2018; Kenpro, 2023). Moreover, another weak link was knowledge transmission. Often, one person in a family was trained to use the biodigester, and thus when this person left the village, any operational know-how that had been secured was lost (Hewitt et al, 2018). Issues such

Biogas buddy Applications

as these seemed to reoccur with each new project. Clearly, keeping a biogas plant in operation requires care, communication and learning for many years after installation.

On a deeper level, these failures revealed to us a persistent blind spot in policy and project design: not enough attention is paid to the long-term success of initiatives. Some literature has pointed to this weak spot; for example, Afridi et al (2023) suggest that project money must be earmarked to guarantee later maintenance work. In many cases, however, once financing is secured and clean cooking equipment is installed, projects are considered more or less complete. In reality, installation is just the beginning. **Ensuring sustained adoption and meaningful integration into communities requires ongoing support, training, and adaptation to local needs.** These aspects are often overlooked or underfunded, likely because long-term engagement and impact measurement are complex and therefore difficult to quantify and report on. Without a shift in focus, many well-intended initiatives risk continuing to fall short of their intended impact.

DESIGNING AN AI SOLUTION

Given these project dynamics, we saw a potential for AI as a tool to boost project success. AI-driven solutions can extend project support and enhance data collection at a low cost, potentially improving long-term outcomes. **By providing adaptive support and monitoring real life use cases, AI can strengthen policy implementation, ensuring sustained impact. Moreover, data gathered through AI can help drive policy learning and inform future projects.** (cf figure)

Our solution, Biogas Buddy, is an app that provides support to biogas users in their local context. It uses predictive AI to troubleshoot daily issues, based on multimedia input from users through images and basic descriptions. Moreover, it can be trained to understand locally available bio inputs and thereby assess water needs and predict issues based on these inputs. It can also be paired with simple and affordable sensors (like pressure or pH) to boost the algorithm’s predictive capacity.

Additionally, by making use of LLM for simple instructions and extensive language capacities, the app can pedagogically guide users through best practices in their own language and using images.

We imagine that the app can give tips to help solve biogas problems before they get severe. For example, it can give reminders for good maintenance care and checks and give advice on what to feed the system to obtain a better gas yield. If a system component breaks, Biogas Buddy can help locate a technician or the right spare part required to fix the system quickly and efficiently. **Biogas Buddy thus ventures beyond technology-centric solutions to development problems. Instead, it boosts the success of existing projects by approaching the nexus of technology, culture and customs in a new way.**

Example use case

A user in India notices that the gas flow in her hob is weak. She opens the Biogas Buddy app and uses her voice to inform the AI of the problem. The app analyses her description and instructs her to a) snap an image of the pH reading and b) take a picture of what she has been feeding into the biogas system. Biogas Buddy then uses these inputs to diagnose the issue based on prediction and provides step-by-step guidance to help the user fix the problem. In this case, the user has overloaded the biogas plant, which has affected the gas flow negatively.

IMPACT

We believe that Biogas Buddy can be particularly impactful in Asia, where there are over 45M household digesters have been installed (Ni, 2024). Moreover, smartphone uptake is relatively high in rural India, with active internet users growing 45% between 2019 and 2023 (WEF, 2023). Our app could also prove a particularly

powerful tool for bridging language barriers in multilingual regions, like Karnataka in India, by using LLM to translate guidance into local languages. Offline support options like text messaging can provide a similar service where internet penetration is lower, like in much of Saharan Africa. With growing internet use across the world, we expect Biogas Buddy to rapidly become more accessible to more people who could benefit from it.

CONCLUSION

Our application of AI to energy focuses on a vital yet often overlooked phase of operations and maintenance. While not as high-profile as project financing or installation, this stage is essential for ensuring long-term success. Biogas Buddy deploys AI in a practical, targeted way to enhance project success by extending support through interactive and personal support, ultimately improving the lives of millions. Small interventions at this stage can have huge impacts and be the difference between policy failure and robust and enduring solutions in the global energy transition. Biogas Buddy illustrates the need to think beyond established narratives around AI. Using a project-focused bottom-up lens, new avenues where AI can make a large positive impact can be found. ■

AI and Disability

Martin Girardin

This article is based on work prepared at the Sciences Po School of Management and Impact (EMI)

Among the 28 million working people aged between 15 and 64, in France, 1.2 million are recognized as having a disability. **This figure inevitably raises the question of the impact of AI on the relationship between employment and disability.**

The French law of February 11, 2005 for equal rights and opportunities (Loi du 11 février 2005 pour l'égalité des droits et des chances) recognizes 6 families of disability:

- motor disability (physical limitations of individuals)
- sensory disability (visual or hearing impairment)
- mental disability
- cognitive impairment (difficulty in processing information)
- mental disability (personality disorders that can affect behavior and/or thinking)

In addition to these categories, disabling illnesses should be included, which can affect activities through severe fatigue.

It is therefore necessary to examine the various systems in place to support people with disabilities in their physical, mental, personal, and professional development.

OPPORTUNITIES OFFERED BY AI FOR PROFESSIONAL INTEGRATION

According to a survey by Agefiph, the association responsible for supporting the development of employment for people with disabilities, by the end of 2023 there will be almost 3 million people with an administrative recognition of disability, representing 7.5% of the working-age population. This survey reveals the inequalities experienced in the professional world. 12% of people with disabilities are unemployed, compared with just 7% of the general public. The average length of time of the unemployment for people with disabilities is 826 days, compared with 634 days for the general public, a difference of 192 days. Only 11% of people with disabilities hold managerial positions, compared to 22% for the general public.

These figures are in line with the work carried out by the British sociologist Mike Olivier, who developed the theory of the 'social model of disability' in 1983. **This model looks beyond the medical condition of patients and sees it as a set of barriers erected by society.** It is these same barriers, including things such as

inaccessible buildings and social prejudices, that take away the autonomy of people with disabilities.

Various technical solutions have been developed to overcome these barriers. The first technical solutions to appear were hardware, physical devices that help people with disabilities in their daily lives. These include haptic feedback technologies for the visually impaired, as well as Braille.

With the rise of New Information and Communication Technologies, new devices, particularly digital ones, have enabled assistance tools to advance even further. For example, applications such as BeMyEyes enable the visually impaired to connect with volunteers who will transcribe what is displayed on camera. Although innovative, these technologies still require human intervention.

The rise of AI represents another step towards autonomy, with the emergence of automated solutions. For example:

- People who are deaf or hard of hearing can use automatic subtitles trained by reinforcement learning.
- AI is used to generate avatars that transcribe information in sign language in real time.

However, for AI to realize its full potential, it is essential to recognize the constraints of these tools.

CHALLENGES AND LIMITS OF AI FOR PROFESSIONAL INTEGRATION

While 65% of people with disabilities see technology overall as an opportunity for employment, their view of AI is more reserved: only 28% of those surveyed see it as an opportunity for employment.

When instruments such as DALL-E are used to create images, the results often tend to be stereotypical. Most images produced with the term 'disabled people' illustrate individuals in wheelchairs, overlooking the variety of disabilities. This could be because these tools are simply created by individuals who will integrate their perception of disability into the tool. According to Asma Mhalla, a researcher specialized in the political and geopolitical issues surrounding technology, "AIs are tools created by humans, for humans".

In addition to biases, the development of AI tools tailored to the needs of people with disabilities is hampered by resource allocation issues. In order to develop reliable tools, companies encounter a high demand for qualified engineers. However, the Joblift recruitment platform estimates that it takes an average of 55 days to fill a permanent position (45% of advertisements) in the artificial intelligence sector in France. This is much longer than in other sectors (33 days on average). This may explain the low presence of such tools in organizations today.

To meet the challenges and risks associated with artificial intelligence technologies, we need to think about the development of these tools in a more collaborative way. **First, integrating people with disabilities into the process of developing AI tools would represent a first step towards AI with less harmful stereotypes and biases towards people with disabilities.** This integration could take the form of including disabled people in workgroups to tackle ethical issues linked to the development of AI. By directly involving users, we can ensure that the technologies developed meet their needs and expectations.

Second, **the development of a common tool, such as an open-source AI, could offer several advantages.** Open source accelerates tool development by pooling developers' efforts. As a result, tools can be developed more quickly, and there is greater transparency as to the data used.

Once these technologies have been developed in an inclusive manner, organizations will be able to integrate them, adapting them to their specific needs. It is then essential to provide training for people using these tools, so that they can use them effectively.

Finally, to ensure that these efforts do not go to waste, it is essential to conduct audits and evaluations. Carrying out these exercises on a regular basis ensures that the AI tools implemented within an organization are reliable, and do not become the source of new inequalities.

Even though AI is lifting some of the barriers to accessibility with image recognition, text summarization, and subtitles, it is not without its drawbacks. The transformation of the world of work is inevitable as AI technologies continue to develop. It is necessary to join forces in a common project to ensure that these tools are put to good use. ■

Complex Biases in Generative AI: Exploring Religious Bias in Stable Diffusion

Giovanni Maggi, Christoph Mautner Markhof, Laura Zurdo, Barbora Bromová, Riccardo Rapparini

This article is based on work prepared at the Sciences Po School of Public Affairs (EAP)

INTRODUCTION

From AI artwork to malicious deep-fakes, generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI) intersects issues of culture, philosophy, economics and politics. Our work, realised in autumn 2022, seeks a more nuanced understanding of less-represented forms of AI bias. It explores religious biases in image-generated AI through the example of Stable Diffusion.

Launched in 2022 by Stability AI, Stable Diffusion provides a machine-learning system to generate images from text based on latent diffusion models (LDMs). The model is trained on a subset of the LAION-5B database: an open dataset composed of 5.8 billion image-text pairs, including 2.3 billion pairs in English and 2.2 billion pairs from over 100 other languages.

Following a review of sources of biases (Section 1) and a methodological note (Section 2), Section 3 empirically analyses outputs across a set of prompts to detect religious biases. Section 4 discusses our findings, exploring how biases interact with Stability AI's core values. **Overall, we find evidence of religious bias such as stereotyping, complex biases, and limited visual reasoning. We posit that Stability AI frames the discussion by both acknowledging open-source's role in amplifying biases and claiming it as necessary for the solution.**

SOURCES OF BIAS IN TEXT-TO-IMAGE GENERATIVE SYSTEMS

In systems like StableDiffusion, bias may arise from two key blocks: Natural Language Processing (NLP, handles prompt interpretation through text-to-latent encoding) and Computer Vision (CV, handles image generation via latent-to-image decoding).

Language Standardisation

There are large differences in how people refer to the same situation (Labov 1972), linked to their sociodemographic characteristics. NLP often fails to detect that language carries secondary information about its speaker (Flek 2020, Hovy & Yang 2021), leading to poorer performance for language forms outside of their training. For instance, models are

commonly trained on established news sources (e.g., the New York Times) and therefore reflect their writers' common characteristics (often educated, white, upper-middle class) (Garimella et al. 2019).

Data Labelling

Bias also stems from data labelling. For instance, annotators may embed the choice of label with subconscious ideological preferences (Planck et al. 2014). Alternatively, the author and annotator's norms may differ (e.g. Sap et al. 2019 argued that African American English is likelier to be labelled as hate speech due to majority white labellers). Similarly, in CV datasets, ill-defined categories can entrench reductive distinctions (Boulamwini and Gebru 2018).

Stereotypical Association

Semantic bias occurs when a model picks up on historical stereotypes represented in the training data and perpetuates them (Garg et al. 2018; Kozłowski et al. 2019). Semantic bias is notoriously difficult to debase (Gonen & Goldberg, 2019), leading Bianchi et al. 2022 to speak of 'complex biases': "pernicious assumptions and power relations" reflected in outputs, like depicting African men in front of a house in a much worse condition than American men.

Research Design

Bias can embed itself in research design. Concentrating research in English and the main Indo-European languages (Joshi et al. 2020) is self-reinforcing: the less information is available, the fewer people will work on modelling a minority context; thus, less data is generated and fewer resources are available (Hovy & Prabhumoye 2021). In the context of religion, less populous belief systems are more likely to be – and remain – under modelled.

METHODOLOGY

Our qualitative analysis focused on eight religion-related categories.¹ Using Stable Diffusion 2, the prompt 'A photo of the face of ___' was combined with a gender-neutral term or a follower of each religion. Additional prompts explored other descriptors: young Judaism, modern Judaism, Jewish women, Sikh women, devoted, religious, good, sinful. 50 images per prompt were generated via Dreamstudio Demo. 20 images per set were randomly picked for analysis.

The output was analysed using elaborative coding, a qualitative method for expanding existing theory through predefined theoretical constructs (Auerbach & Silverstein, 2003). We focused on stereotype amplification, drawing from Bianchi et al.'s 2022 'complex biases' framework, and labelling bias, referencing Cho et al.'s 2022 work on visual reasoning skills. These served as the framework for identifying religious biases.³ As a 'top-down' approach, elaborative coding guided the analysis towards recurring themes grouped into categories under this framework. The next section presents each concept with their respective categories.

OUTPUT ANALYSIS

General Stereotypes and Stereotype Amplification

The **outputs display a wide range of stereotype amplification, where real-life correlations between certain features like gender are made more prominent than they really are** (Quilliam & Pager, 2010). **Thus, the outputs displayed almost exclusively masculine features** (Figure 1), even though the gender split in religions is relatively even. This may be a general bias present throughout the system (Bianchi et al, 2022) or could point to women's unequal standing in religious contexts, since most religions over-represent men in authority positions.

[Figure 1]

However, the images do not display certain negative stereotypes held against some religions. Since Western media coverage of terrorist events often creates harmful associations with Islam (Sutkute, 2019), such a stereotype could have been reflected in the outputs. This was not the case – at least in the sample generated for this paper.

In terms of ethnicity, most religions were represented by their majority cultural origin. Muslims appeared Middle Eastern. Sikhs and Hindus depicted as of Indian descent, Shintoists were Japanese, and Buddhists, East Asian. Jews and Atheists were white, while Christianity was the only religion with black, mixed and white followers. The aspect of a 'World Religion' is therefore seemingly only applied to Christianity.

[Figures 1 & 2]

Complex Biases in Diffusion Outputs

The model also exhibited signs of complex biases, associating certain religious groups with a particular set of backgrounds or circumstances. This was apparent for Judaism: the images generated distinctly resembled early 20th century monochrome portraits. This tendency to represent Judaism as archaic could not be mitigated by prompt rewriting, even upon adding descriptors like "young" or "modern" (Figure 3). Meanwhile, the historicization of Judaism has been rejected by various Jewish organisations, who claim that recognising Judaism only in relation to its fraught and traumatic history is reductive (Skrodzka et al, 2022).

[Figure 3]

Complex biases also appeared at play with terms like 'devoted'. **Almost all images of a 'devoted person' depict women, possibly amplifying the stereotype of women as more peaceful and virtuous.** Furthermore, devotion could also be seen as a devotion to husbands, further pointing towards the women's 'pure and subordinated' role in society [Figure 4]

Limited Visual Reasoning Skills

Visual reasoning refers to the ability to identify objects, count their quantities, and accurately portray the relation between them (Cho et al. 2022). **Yet, in the case of Buddhism, 85% of all of the model's outputs were photo-realistic pictures of statues; not people** (Figure 1). The model also struggled with generating accurate religious accessories, especially if their use is gendered. When working with Muslim headscarves and Hindu facial markings, it frequently pictured masculine faces with accessories usually worn by women [Figure 1].

HOW TO MOVE FORWARD

The outputs above are biased when they misrepresent social groups, essentialize gender attributes, and perpetuate Western systems as the norm (e.g. Christianity as the only 'World Religion'). The sources of bias explored in the first section of this analysis explain possible reasons for this. First, Stable Diffusion was trained on an English-language dataset (Stability AI, n.d.). Plus, the model exacerbated religious symbols - perhaps because annotators only labelled an item as 'religious' when the signs were very visible, causing the system to yield an exaggerated view of religious symbols.

Stability AI is open about bias in Stable Diffusion yet operationalises these concerns in a unique way. While OpenAI's DALL·E 2 is closed sourced with various guardrails, Stable Diffusion users can access the code and weights and create forks with few safety constraints (Stability AI, 2022a). Underpinning this is a normative view that prioritises openness and trusts the community to solve ethical issues. This extends to religion: if the Stable Diffusion model is biased due to Western datasets, open sourcing would allow others to recreate it (Kilcher, 2022). Thus, Stability AI's vision is not of one generalist model, but of multiple culturally specific ones.

Is there a meaningful opportunity to retrain Stable Diffusion? **Stability AI's vision for decentralised models requires, beyond modifying the code and weights, retraining an entire algorithm.** This is not the cheapest solution: Stable Diffusion v1 reportedly cost 600 000€ to train (Mostaque, 2022). The community seems to be attempting to circumvent these limits organically and create "retrainable-ish model[s]" (TheLastBen, 2022), with tools like Invoke AI (Foong, 2022) or fast-stable-diffusion (TheLastBen, 2022). Furthermore, Stability AI provides grants and computing power for

selected projects (Biewald, 2022). **While these efforts arguably help paint its open sourced approach in a positive light, it is unclear whether "retrainable-ish" is enough to achieve Stability AI's vision and solution to AI biases.**

CONCLUSION

Following its release in 2022, research into Stable Diffusion was quick to suggest the presence of algorithmic bias. Building on this research, this paper focused on religious bias. Following a qualitative analysis using elaborative coding, we found that Stable Diffusion amplifies stereotypes, exhibits signs of complex biases, and of poor visual reasoning.

Furthermore, we situated the observed biases within Stability AI's governance approach. Stability AI believes that, while Stable Diffusion may perpetuate bias, the open-source approach will produce a net benefit in the long term, allowing communities to build representative models. **Whether or not this future materializes, providers' governance practices are shaping the AI landscape with implications on public interest and trust.** ■

Figure 1: Samples of images generated using the prompt 'A photo of the face of a ___' alongside four belief systems: Christianity, Buddhism, Hinduism, and Islam.

Figure 2: Examples of images generated using the prompt 'A photo of the face of a ___' alongside four belief systems: Judaism, Sikhism, Shintoism, and Atheism.

Figure 3: Examples of images generated by modifying the initial prompt with specifications of time period or gender.

Figure 4: Examples of images generated by modifying the initial prompt to refer to religious or normative status without specifying a belief system.

Part 3

CITIZENS AND AI : A QUESTION OF TRUST

Closely linked to one of the AI Summit's major questions about trust in AI, we now turn to how AI is impacting citizens' day-to-day lives—through hiring algorithms, welfare fraud detection systems, or public policymaking tools. AI systems increasingly make high-stakes decisions, yet those affected—often the most vulnerable—have little insight into how these decisions are made or recourse. Austria's AMS system and the Dutch SyRI case illustrate how opaque or biased AI systems can deepen existing social inequities. Accountability mechanisms are still lacking: most citizens don't know when AI is being used, and don't have access to appeals or human reviews. Transparency without enforcement is hollow. Finally, public opinion is divided: new studies show growing polarization between AI enthusiasts and skeptics. Enthusiasts support automation in public services, while skeptics demand robust safeguards and democratic oversight. We question here whether trust in AI can be built on transparency alone and show that democratic and trustworthy AI requires real accountability, clear redress systems, and inclusive governance that reflects public values.

Building Accountability: Transparency, Explainability and Appeal Processes: The Case of AMS Austria

Eleonora Bonel, Aahil Sheikh, Devon Nir, and Laura Zurdo

This article is based on work prepared at the Sciences Po School of Public Affairs (EAP)

INTRODUCTION

The Austrian public employment service (Arbeitsmarktservice, or AMS) plays a central role in guiding job seekers through the labour market by offering advice, training, and financial support (AMS, 2020). In pursuit of greater efficiency and sustainable employment reintegration, the AMS adopted a semi-automated profiling system (AMAS) to assess job seekers' labour market prospects. Trained on historical data and launched in 2018 for implementation in 2021, this algorithm classified individuals into three support categories based on their predicted "integration chances" (IC). However, the system quickly became a focal point of public scrutiny. Critics raised concerns about the lack of transparency, the use of repurposed and potentially biased data, and the discriminatory implications of its design.

This article examines how the AMS algorithm exemplifies the challenges of embedding algorithmic decision-making in public services, and it was presented at the AI Action Summit by Sciences Po under the theme "Public Interest AI". It explores the system's failures in transparency and fairness, and argues for the necessity of explainability and robust appeal processes to ensure accountability in algorithmic governance.

METHOD

Accountability generally refers to the processes and mechanisms whereby an actor justifies their conduct to a forum, which decides if the actor was virtuous in their conduct. In public management theory, accountability is a tool to improve the results of public action (Zumofen, 2016). In 'responsible tech', accountability is deeply intertwined with transparency, auditability, and the capacity to contest algorithmic decisions and seek redress. In the case of Austria's Public Employment Service (AMS) algorithm, accountability was a point of significant contention. Civil society groups criticized the system's opacity and the absence of meaningful

oversight. Although the project initially proceeded without adequate checks, public pressure ultimately resulted in the intervention of Austria's Data Protection Authority (DPA), an Ombudsman inquiry, and a parliamentary investigation—mechanisms that exposed weaknesses in the system and compelled the AMS to release partial documentation. Although the project initially proceeded without adequate checks, public pressure ultimately resulted in the intervention of Austria's Data Protection Authority (DPA), an Ombudsman inquiry and a parliamentary investigation—mechanisms that exposed weaknesses in the system and compelled the AMS to release partial documentation.

To systematically assess how accountability was maintained—or breached—we apply a modified version of the Framework for Algorithmic Accountability in the Public Sector (2021) (refer to Table 1), developed by the Ada Lovelace Institute, AI Now Institute and the Open Government Partnership. This methodology focuses on dimensions such as transparency, audit processes, impact assessments and human oversight. **Through this framework, the analysis revealed significant deficiencies, particularly in transparency and the insufficient implementation of the "human in the loop" principle. Crucially, the study positions accountability not as an external corrective, but as an internal principle that must be embedded in algorithmic design from the outset.** Epistemologically, our analysis builds upon this work and challenges the techno-optimistic assumption that AI systems yield neutral or equitable outcomes, arguing instead that **algorithms are socio-technical artifacts shaped by human choices, systemic biases and contextual factors. The AMS case exemplifies how technocratic approaches focused narrowly on efficiency can entrench structural discrimination, reinforcing the need for critically informed, socially accountable AI governance.**

Mechanism	Description
<i>Principles and guidelines</i>	High-level goals and how they may be implicated in the use of algorithmic systems in the public sector. Normative standards against which to evaluate the use of algorithms.
<i>Transparency</i>	E.g., registries, source transparency, logic explanation. Two dimensions: - Inward transparency: Openness within the organisation as to what choices are made and why. - Outward transparency: Formal and meaningful engagement with relevant stakeholders.
<i>Impact assessments</i>	Prior to the launch or ongoing, typically an internal self-assessment. Broad assessment not only of the algorithm's technical aspects but also of how it interacts with its environment (policies, users, affected citizens...)
<i>Audits and regulatory inspections</i>	Concurrently or after. Can be conducted by a third-party (external, output assessment), second-party (external hire, backend-outputs), or first-party. Audits examine technical elements, while regulatory inspections assess the system against a normative standard.
<i>Independent oversight</i>	Independent bodies that oversee and direct the use of algorithmic systems by public agencies. Monitor the actions of public bodies and make recommendations, sanctions, or decisions.
<i>Right to hearing and appeals; Human in the loop</i>	Procedural fairness assumes that individuals are in a position to identify a deviation from the norm and change their decision, or challenge the deviation. Effective right to appeal + effective human in the loop (which implies considering how algorithms influence humans and organisational decision-making structures)

Table 1: Adapted framework - 6 selected accountability mechanisms

Figure 1 by the authors- Adapted framework- 6 selected accountability mechanisms

RESULTS

Ultimately, the project's accountability mechanisms proved inadequate. Accountability was not the result of deliberate planning by the AMS but emerged through Austria's legal infrastructure and civil society activism. That stakeholders managed to uncover significant issues, despite 94 of 96 models remaining undisclosed, demonstrates how even limited transparency can be impactful. However, reliance on external safeguards is precarious, as their strength varies by context. **Responsible algorithmic systems should embed accountability from the outset, rather than depend on external intervention. In this light, the AMS case serves as a cautionary tale, not a model of accountability.**

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE ACTIONS

The recommendations from our analysis are grouped into four thematic areas, summarized in Figure 2. These draw on critical literature such as Ananny and Crawford (2018), which challenges the sufficiency of transparency as an ideal. In the AMS case, achieving basic transparency was inadequate; more robust, layered mechanisms are needed to ensure meaningful accountability. While explained briefly here, these are discussed in detail in the full research paper.

(1) Ex-ante measures: Transparency alone does not guarantee accountability. AMS should have adopted a structured accountability framework from the outset. This could have included layered audits—such as governance audits, which assess whether system objectives and decision-making logics are understood by both users and those affected (DRCF, 2022: 15). Tools like AI regulatory sandboxes, testing beds, and living labs could have served as controlled environments to assess

system impact, iterate designs, and include diverse stakeholders—especially civil society groups like Digital Society Austria—before deployment.

(2) Human oversight: AMS framed the algorithm as a decision-support tool, suggesting caseworkers would weigh it alongside qualitative factors like soft skills. First, the algorithm was conceptualised as a “project to increase efficiency” (Allhutter et al., 2020, p. 9) rather than accuracy, leading to conflicting expectations. Caseworkers were implicitly incentivized to accept algorithmic output uncritically to meet efficiency targets (Allhutter et al., 2020). **A user interaction study could have surfaced these tensions, revealing how design and deployment incentives shaped behaviour on the ground.**

(3) Ex-post assessment: Post-deployment algorithmic audits—ranging from compliance checks to reliability reviews—are critical for ongoing accountability. These audits, akin to financial audits, help ensure algorithms are lawful, ethical and safe (Koshiyama et al. 2021). **The field of AI auditing, especially in the context of the EU AI Act, presents a nuanced landscape of assurance risks as it expands into third-party auditors, ranging from traditional consultancies to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).** Given the overlap of privacy, data protection, and AI, the research paper also examines the right to explanation and how it ties into the GDPR and the AI Act.

(4) Public transparency: The concept of algorithmic accountability necessitates the presence of a critical audience for true accountability. This involves nurturing greater digital literacy to help the public understand the impact and nuances of algorithms and automated systems. In the case of the AMS, this critical audience was overlooked, not due to a lack of identifiable actors but due to governance oversights. The wide array of potential contributors, including scientists, politicians, social partners, and administrators, clearly demonstrated their engagement capacity through the 2022 "Stop the AMS algorithm" campaign. This initiative, which included the creation of a dedicated information website with FOIA request options, exemplifies the kind of active, inclusive approach needed for genuine transparency.

Although no single model fits all contexts, the AMS case illustrates a broader trend: the push for technological efficiency in public administration often outpaces accountability mechanisms. Techno-solutionism in public management may be difficult to eradicate, especially amid intensifying global competition around digital innovation. Yet, meaningful accountability is not incompatible with innovation.

Ex-ante measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accountability and transparency frameworks • Algorithmic system assessment • Scenario planning and risk assessments
Human oversight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User interaction study on human involvement
Ex-post assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rights to explanation • Regulator auditing and risk assessments
Public transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work with critical audiences and build relationships • Algorithmic registries, mapping & allowing for public feedback

Figure 2 by the authors - Summary of recommendations

Embedding transparency, civic participation, and human rights impact assessments from the outset is not only feasible—it is essential for building public trust and ensuring the legitimacy of algorithmic governance. ■

Ensuring the Right to Effective Remedies in Welfare: The Case of the Dutch SyRI

Stavroula (Stavrina) Chousou

This article is based on work prepared at the Sciences Po School of Public Affairs (EAP)

ISSUE AT HAND - OBJECTIVE OF THIS PAPER

The SyRI (System Risk Identification) algorithm exemplifies how the poor deployment of technology can deepen public crises, highlighting the need to rethink standard requirements for public Algorithmic Decision-Making (ADM) systems in the EU. The focus on public ADM is incremental, as citizens are particularly vulnerable in their interactions with the state due to the significant impact of public decisions on their rights, legal status and access to services, combined with their comparatively limited power to challenge said decisions.

Introduced in the Netherlands in 2003 to detect welfare and tax fraud, SyRI relied on opaque, automated processes with high false positive rates. Despite concerns, a 2013 law granted it broad access to personal data from 17 public authorities, primarily targeting high-poverty areas. Nearly 100,000 people were wrongfully labelled as fraudulent and forced to repay large sums (van Schendel, 2022; Brouwer, 2023). Lacking resources to challenge these decisions, many faced severe financial and emotional hardship, notably wrongful foster care placements and even suicides (Huissen, 2021). The "Suspected in Advance" campaign raised awareness, leading to a 2020 court ruling that found SyRI violated privacy rights under GDPR. However, compensation remains uncertain (Huissen yt video and interview). SyRI's greatest flaw was its lack of contestability, leaving victims trapped in a system they could neither comprehend nor challenge for 7 years, compiling unjust harm and causing irreparable damage as a result.

This paper attempted to answer the question: How can future SyRI cases be avoided? In other words, **how can we ensure contestability in state-citizen transactions where public ADM is a significant component, while addressing a growing justice gap shaped by both technology literacy and resource inequality?**

Laying down ABCs of effective remedies and contestability

The right to an effective remedy is fundamental in the EU, allowing citizens to challenge arbitrary state actions through accessible mechanisms (Article 47,

Charter of Fundamental Rights; Article 19, TEU). Contestability — the ability to challenge decisions — is key to ensuring meaningful remedies. It involves a) **Notice**: Knowing the decision parameters, b) **Explanation**: Understanding the 'why' and 'how' and c) **Challenge & Correction**: Having the means to contest and rectify decisions. In ADM, limited contestability often arises from conceptual flaws in models or datasets, such as the use of fully black-box architectures. Other forms of negligence—like unclear instructions, inadequate notice, limited information about the tool or lack of channels for contestation—significantly contribute to this issue. Additional barriers, including cost, time constraints, technical complexity and skill gaps across professions, further prevent courts, auditors and even AI operators from fully understanding AI-driven decisions or improving tools to trace how those decisions were made (Eubanks, 2018; Veale & Brass, 2019).

METHOD

To address the research question, the author reviewed socio-technical literature on ADM to identify current practices, limitations and trends. **The analysis underscored the need for institutional change in how AI is integrated into decision-making—not as a human replacement, but as an assistive tool governed by clear organizational processes.** Regulatory frameworks in the EU, particularly the AI Act and GDPR, were examined to clarify public sector obligations and translate them into an actionable plan that embeds contestability as a core design principle.

PROPOSING A ROAD AHEAD

The EU regulatory landscape offers key guidance for implementing contestability in automated decision-making (ADM), though notable gaps remain. Currently, the only EU-wide liability framework is the revised Product Liability Directive (PLD), which introduces strict liability for operators of AI systems (European Commission, 2022). Under this regime, manufacturers are liable for harm caused by defective products regardless of fault. However, there is limited guidance or jurisprudence on how these principles apply specifically to AI systems. National liability regimes may also apply in

sector-specific contexts such as consumer protection or administrative law, depending on how the AI system is used.

On the other hand, the EU AI Act (Regulation 2024/1689), a product safety regulation, sets conformity obligations for AI operators. While it does not establish liability, non-compliance can support liability claims under various liability laws and can trigger fines of up to 7% of global turnover. Public bodies using ADM systems typically act as deployers, but may also function as other operators under the Act. This paper details how public ADM operators can meet explainability and contestability obligations under Article 86 of the AI Act, Article 22 of the GDPR, and Article 47 of the EU Charter. The link between contestability, meaningful information on algorithmic decisions and access to remedies was established in this paper in 2023, but [Case C-806/24](#), brought before the ECJ in late 2024, reaffirmed this connection in a strikingly practical case.

Based on these legal benchmarks, the paper proposes the following action plan for public authorities aiming to responsibly integrate ADM into decision-making processes, while also addressing EU deployers' duties relating to human oversight (Article 14) and, potentially, transparency (Article 50) obligations.

(1) Define the required elements of your ADM

- Clearly define the covered datasets, the scope of use of the AI system and its role in the final decision.
- Describe the steps of the decision-making process, its parameters and exemptions, if applicable. Describe the impact of the AI system in the process and its relation to the human decision-makers.
- Establish AI literacy programs for employees (Article 4 of the AI Act) and corresponding specialised training for AI-operating or affected personnel.

(2) Establish Clear Notice Mechanisms

- Ensure clear and accessible information about the AI-generated aspects of a decision (Article 50 of the EU AI Act; Article 22 of the GDPR; ECJ Case C-203/22). This can be a simple notice (e.g. Some aspects of the decision were co-generated by AI) or an annex explaining its impact in more detail.
- Deploy human information assistants who can bridge technical language, clarify concepts and ensure that individuals understand the process and their rights. Provide them with appropriate training and support material per the relevant requirements.

(3) Develop Meaningful Explanations for Decisions

- Ensure that significant ADM decisions are accompanied by sufficient explanations of *how* and *why* decisions are made, highlighting its

use, as defined in the first step (Article 86 of the EU AI Act). Note that a simple notice of AI use, albeit necessary, does not suffice as an explanation of a significant outcome.

The role of explanation should be analysed in the context of the Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment imposed by the AI Act, to identify the proper information to be included. The decision should encompass clear instructions about how the recipient can contest it, based on the available procedures of contestation described in the next section.

(4) Develop Intuitive Media for Contestation

Contestation pathways should mirror the range of potential violations, offering options such as requesting further clarification, appealing decisions, involving a third-party mediator and, if necessary, pursuing a fair trial in court. To support this, organizations must proactively:

- Establish parallel human review processes to detect errors, allow corrections and handle appeals.
- Develop accessible, user-friendly interfaces to make contestation easier and more intuitive by setting up direct communication channels with responsible personnel and enabling decision-tracking features.
- Introduce instant-feedback mechanisms so citizens can submit new or missing information, allowing reviewers to adjust decisions and notify users accordingly.
- Provide a user portal where citizens can connect, seek advice and coordinate collective action (e.g. class actions). This should include contact information for pro bono or low-cost legal and advocacy support.
- Deploy human information assistants to explain decision-making steps and facilitate contact with the appropriate departments. This ensures both smooth interface management and essential human support, especially for citizens with limited digital literacy (e.g. the elderly).

(5) Foster Civil Society Involvement

- Encourage public organizations to work with external organizations, like think tanks, independent auditors and NGOs to assess and critique ADM systems from their conception.
- Create feedback channels for scrutiny, available to the cooperating experts as well as the recipients of ADM decisions, creating 'critical audiences' evaluators (e.g. in the interface).

(6) Introduce 'Liable Until You Empower' Framework - Policy Suggestion

- Require public authorities to bear the burden of actively empowering individuals throughout the decision-making process. Insufficient engagement or proof could result in penalties.

FINAL REMARKS

This paper proposes a framework to strengthen the right to effective remedies in EU public ADM processes focusing on organizational and regulatory solutions. It deliberately limits its scope to a general framework for public entities, without addressing specific sectoral nuances. As ADM becomes more prevalent in public decision-making, it increasingly affects populations with limited AI literacy and restricted access to legal remedies. **Ensuring accessible explanations, legal support, and institutional contestability is essential to uphold the right to effective remedies in this context. ■**

Understanding Public Opinion on AI Policy-Making Using POL.IS

Marta Antunes, Janina Morstin, Kai Mütschele & My-Han Trinh

This article is based on work prepared at the Sciences Po School of Public Affairs (EAP)

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is everywhere, shaping our world and sparking controversial debate across the globe. Yet, while much scholarly attention has been paid to fields such as AI governance (Taeihagh, 2021), the future of work in times of AI (Deranty & Corbin, 2024) or AI's environmental impact (Wang, 2024), we were interested in analysing an often-overlooked topic: public opinion on AI usage. Using the participatory platform Pol.is, we started a public discussion on the usage of AI technologies in policymaking processes. **Our aim was to get citizens' input on what constitutes beneficial, acceptable or, on the contrary, harmful use cases of AI in policymaking processes and on what basis citizens make such distinctions.** We then propose four recommendations for regulating the integration of AI tools into policymaking processes - whether on a local, national, European or global scale.

THE PROJECT

As part of a Sciences Po class entitled "Governance, Democracy and Public Policy: Digital Democracy and Public Spaces", taught by Professor Gianluca Sgueo, groups of students were tasked to use the participatory online platform Pol.is to initiate, moderate and evaluate a public discussion on a subject of their choice. Our team chose to focus on a specific use case of AI - policymaking processes, which are particularly interesting for several reasons: First, data confirms that this is not just a theoretical discussion but a highly relevant issue, as **AI is already widely used in policymaking worldwide.** For instance, a recent report shows that 23 out of 30 OECD countries (77%) employ AI in internal processes, public service design and delivery and policymaking (OECD, 2024). Second, especially when it comes to the usage of AI in democratic processes such as policymaking, **we argue that citizen input is not only crucial but even mandatory to ensure the preservation of legitimacy as a cornerstone of democratic decision-making.** Hence, while many governments already utilise AI in policymaking processes or are developing plans to do so, citizen input on this topic is long overdue.

WHAT IS POL.IS AND HOW DOES IT WORK?

To explore public opinion on this topic, we used the interactive platform Pol.is, which facilitates open and dynamic online deliberations. Its machine learning features help identify areas of consensus and disagreement among participants. Pol.is requires the design and formulation of seed statements, with which participants can engage by agreeing, disagreeing or disregarding them. The 28 seed statements that we designed to initiate the discussion on AI each corresponded to a stage of the policy cycle (based on Howlett et al., 1995).

When crafting these statements, we ensured a balanced mix of for- and against-AI perspectives to prevent bias and avoid steering participants in a particular direction. The statements were deliberately formulated as applied examples for the use of AI in policymaking and did not require any prior knowledge of political processes or technical understanding of AI. **By translating such "expert knowledge" into easy-to-understand statements we ensured that our Pol.is discussion was as inclusive and accessible as possible.** Furthermore, we allowed participants to submit their own statements to the platform, to which others could then react. This further increased the discussion's interactivity, which was moderated by our team to ensure a constructive and respectful debate.

RESULTS

In total, 107 participants contributed 2,597 votes on the proposed statements, averaging 24.27 votes per person. This high level of engagement reflects both strong interest in the topic and active participation on the platform. Further supporting this interpretation, we allowed 48 additional statements to be submitted, demonstrating a strong demand for expressing diverse opinions. Overall, the discussion was highly dynamic and interactive. Pol.is then uses machine learning to cluster participants into groups based on shared viewpoints and detected areas of consensus and disagreement. **Our analysis identified two distinct groups among participants: based on their characteristics we named them “AI enthusiasts” and “AI sceptics.”** AI enthusiasts (52 participants) were more open to integrating AI into policymaking and generally had greater confidence in its technical capabilities. In contrast, AI sceptics (36 participants) were more hesitant about the deployment of AI across all stages of the policy cycle and fundamentally questioned the functionalities attributed to AI.

LIMITATIONS

Several limitations of our project need to be discussed, as they also provide inspiration for improving the design and features of the Pol.is platform. First and foremost, while our theoretical framework allowed for a clear structuring of seed statements along the policy cycle, Pol.is did not allow for a logical sequencing of statements as they were automatically randomised for every participant. This led to some confusion among participants. We recommend Pol.is introduce an option for moderators to determine the order of the questions in advance. Second, given the ambitious timeframe of our project, we based the interpretation of our results on a limited sample size. Moreover, as the participants' pool was mostly confined to our own networks, we must assume a limited representativeness of the sample. This points to another structural weakness of Pol.is: the platform does not allow for the gathering of basic data on the discussion's participants (such as age, gender or education). This further limits the generalisability of our outcome and makes future research on correlations between such variables and citizen's voting behaviour impossible.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Taking into consideration these limitations, our project nevertheless points towards several interesting results, which provide valuable insights into public opinion on the use of AI in policymaking processes. The four suggestions made in the following section are lessons from our project that, if adhered to in attempts to formulate binding rules for the use of AI within the policy cycle, will contribute to their legitimacy by

embedding them into an analysis of citizens' opinions.

First, regardless of whether people are sceptical or enthusiastic about the use of AI in policymaking processes, both these groups equally emphasised the need for human oversight and the proper training of civil servants in handling AI. In other words, **citizens seem to demand what could be called a constructive vigilance in implementing and utilising AI in areas that are as sensitive as policymaking.**

Second, **introducing AI within the policymaking processes ought to focus on the stages of “policy formulation” and “policy evaluation” as citizens seem to be most open towards AI's usage in these contexts.** For instance, many participants were in favour of using AI to continuously track the performance of new projects, such as whether a new traffic law is in fact reducing accidents by analysing available real-time traffic data. Another popular statement proposed using AI to study large health data sets to identify patterns, such as the rise of certain diseases, to help formulate policies that improve public health.

Third, by contrast, **the areas in which AI involvement was least popular were those of “agenda-setting” and “policy maintenance.”** For example, citizens overwhelmingly disagreed with the statement that AI should be used to analyse and balance multiple factors, such as job creation, environmental protection, and budget limits when deciding on major infrastructure projects. Similarly, citizens seem to value the human element in administrative processes as they disagree that it is better to use AI to respond to citizen's inquiries.

Lastly, and perhaps most importantly, our project has clearly shown that **citizens care about the various use cases of AI and, in particular, the role of these systems in democratic processes such as policymaking.** This leads us to a concrete call for action: **Not only is it important to have a public debate about the use of AI in policymaking, but - precisely because this concerns democratic processes - it is crucial to place citizens and their opinions at the very centre of this debate. ■**

BIBLIOGRAPHY

PART 1

FROM SCARCITY TO SCALE : CROSS-BORDER DATA FLOWS FOR ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Fondation Robert Schuman. "Digital Legislation: Convergence or Divergence of Models? A Comparative Look at the European Union, China, and the United States." *European Issues*, 25 mai 2021. <https://www.robert-schuman.eu/en/european-issues/769-digital-legislation-convergence-or-divergence-of-models-a-comparative-look-at-the-european-union-china-and-the-united-states>.

OECD. The Path to Becoming a Data-Driven Public Sector. *OECD Publishing*, 2021. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/the-path-to-becoming-a-data-driven-public-sector_059814a7-en.html.

The Economist. "The World's Most Valuable Resource Is No Longer Oil but Data." *The Economist*, 6 may 2017. <https://www.economist.com/leaders/2017/05/06/the-worlds-most-valuable-resource-is-no-longer-oil-but-data>.

OECD. Recommendation on Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data (OECD Legal Instrument No. 0406). *OECD Legal Instruments*, 2021. <https://legalinstruments.oecd.org/en/instruments/OECD-LEGAL-0406/>.

OECD. Mapping Commonalities in Regulatory Approaches to Cross-Border Data Transfers. *OECD Publishing*, 2023. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/mapping-commonalities-in-regulatory-approaches-to-cross-border-data-transfers_ca9f974e-en.html.

Congressional Research Service. "Cross-Border Data Sharing and Protection: An Analysis." 2019. <https://sgp.fas.org/crs/misc/R45584.pdf>.

Suresh, Harini, and John Guttag. "A Framework for Understanding Unintended Consequences of Machine Learning." arXiv preprint, January 2020. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2001.08361>.

Wang, Li, et al. "Ethics in AI: Perspectives and Challenges." arXiv preprint, November 2022. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.04325>.

Tan, Xiaohu, et al. "Emerging Trends in Artificial Intelligence Regulation." arXiv preprint, December 2024. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.17847>.

Davis, Tim. "The State of Privacy Laws in the United States." *The New York Times: Wirecutter Blog*, April 2025. <https://www.nytimes.com/wirecutter/blog/state-of-privacy-laws-in-us/>.

WILL TRESPASSERS BE PROSECUTED? A REVIEW OF PRIVACY RIGHTS IN THE AGE OF AI

Privacy (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy). <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/privacy/>.
“Privacy in an AI Era: How Do We Protect Our Personal Information?” Stanford HAI.
<https://hai.stanford.edu/news/privacy-ai-era-how-do-we-protect-our-personal-information>.

Solove, Daniel J. *Understanding Privacy*. Harvard University Press, 2008 :
- “Nothing to Hide: The False Tradeoff Between Privacy and Security.” ResearchGate,
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228139465_Nothing_to_Hide_The_False_Tradeoff_Between_Privacy_and_Security
- “Artificial Intelligence and Privacy: SSRN”.
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4713111.
- “The Limitations of Privacy Rights.” SSRN Electronic Journal, 2022. DOI.org (Crossref),
<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4024790>.

“General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Compliance Guidelines.” *GDPR.Eu*,
<https://gdpr.eu/>.

Justice K.S.Puttaswamy(Retd) And Anr. Vs Union Of India And Ors. on 24 August, 2017.
<https://indiankanoon.org/doc/91938676/>. *Supreme court of India, on Ikanoon.org*

Nissim, Kobbi, and Alexandra Wood. “Is Privacy Privacy?” *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, vol. 376, no. 2128, Aug. 2018, p. 20170358. royalsocietypublishing.org (Atypon), <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2017.0358>.

Shoshana Zuboff. *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism*. Hachette Book Group.
<https://www.hachettebookgroup.com/titles/shoshana-zuboff/the-age-of-surveillance-capitalism/9781610395694/?lens=publicaffairs>.

THE NEW INFORMATION ECONOMY: FAIR TRAINING AND COPYRIGHT IN THE EU

Autorité de Concurrence (2024) *Avis 24-A-05 du 28 juin 2024 relatif au fonctionnement concurrentiel du secteur de l'intelligence artificielle générative*. [online]. Available from: <https://www.autoritedelaconcurrence.fr/fr/avis/relatif-au-fonctionnement-concurrentiel-du-secteur-de-lintelligence-artificielle-generative> (Accessed 30 April 2025).

De la Durantaye, K. (2024) "Control and Compensation. A Comparative Analysis of Copyright Exceptions for Training Generative AI." [online]. Available from: <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=5021889>

Havlikova, S. (2025) "Technical Challenges of Rightsholders' Opt-out From Gen AI Training after Robert Kneschke v. LAION". *JIPITEC – Journal of Intellectual Property, Information Technology and E-Commerce Law*. 16 (1), . [online]. Available from: <https://www.jipitec.eu/jipitec/article/view/422>

Jiménez, J. (2024) "AI, Robots.txt. AI, Robots.txt." (Internet Architecture Board (IAB)), . [online]. Available from: <https://www.ietf.org/slides/slides-aicontrolws-ai-robotstxt-00.pdf>.

Yonadav, S. (2024) "Practices for Governing Agentic AI Systems" [online]. Available from: <https://openai.com/index/practices-for-governing-agentic-ai-systems/> (Accessed 30 April 2025).

PART 2

DEPLOYING AI FOR ENERGY ACCESS

Afridi, Z. U. R., Ullah, K., Mustafa, M. F., Saleem, H., Shaker, B., Ashraf, N., & Aslam, S. (2023b). "Biogas as sustainable approach for social uplift in South East Asian Region". *Energy Reports*, 10, 4808–4818. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyrs.2023.11.037>

Batchu, V. (2024, December 12). "Satellite powered estimation of global solar potential." <https://research.google/blog/satellite-powered-estimation-of-global-solar-potential/>

Chen, Y., Yang, G., Sweeney, S., & Feng, Y. (2009). "Household biogas use in rural China: A study of opportunities and constraints". *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 14(1), 545–549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2009.07.019>

Clemens, H., Bailis, R., Nyambane, A., & Ndung'u, V. (2018). "Africa Biogas Partnership Program: A review of clean cooking implementation through market development in East Africa". *Energy Sustainable Development/Energy for Sustainable Development*, 46, 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2018.05.012>

ECPA. (2022, April 28). "The persistent challenge of access to Clean Cooking" - ECPA - *Energy and Climate Partnership of the Americas*. <https://ecpamericas.org/newsletters/the-persistent-challenge-of-access-to-clean-cooking/>

Hewitt, J., Holden, M., Robinson, B., Jewitt, S., & Clifford, M. (2022). "Not quite cooking on gas: Understanding biogas plant failure and abandonment in Northern Tanzania." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 165, 112600. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112600>

IEA. (n.d.). "Access to clean cooking – SDG7: Data and Projections" – *Analysis - IEA*. <https://www.iea.org/reports/sdg7-data-and-projections/access-to-clean-cooking>

Kenpro. (2023, April 26). "Maintenance and troubleshooting of a fixed dome biogas plant." <https://www.kenpro.org/maintenance-and-troubleshooting-of-a-fixed-dome-biogas-plant/>

Ni, J. (2024). "A review of household and industrial anaerobic digestion in Asia: Biogas development and safety incidents." *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 197, 114371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2024.114371>

Roubík, H., Mazancová, J., Banout, J., & Verner, V. (2015). "Addressing problems at small-scale biogas plants: a case study from central Vietnam". *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 112, 2784–2792. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.09.114>

Uwamahoro, D. (2021). "IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF EXISTING BIOGAS PLANTS IN RWANDA." CASE STUDY: KAYONZA DISTRICT. *University of Rwanda*. <https://dr.ur.ac.rw/bitstream/handle/123456789/1948/UWAMAHORO%20Denise.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

WHO. (2024, October 24). "Types of pollutants". <https://www.who.int/teams/environment-climate-change-and-health/air-quality-and-health/health-impacts/types-of-pollutants>

World Economic Forum. (2023, December 27). "Using smartphones to boost digital literacy among India's rural communities". <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2023/12/how-smartphones-can-boost-digital-literacy-among-indias-rural-communities/>

AI AND DISABILITY

Kerroumi, Bachir, et Stéphane Forgeron. "Le modèle social du handicap." *Espace éthique Île-de-France*, 16 décembre 2019. <https://www.espace-ethique.org/ressources/article/le-modele-social-du-handicap>.

Aivancity. "Lancement du livre blanc consacré à l'IA au service du handicap au travail." *Aivancity*, mai 2025. <https://www.aivancity.ai/lancement-du-livre-blanc-consacre-lia-au-service-du-handicap-au-travail>.

Ministère du Travail, de la Santé, des Solidarités et des Familles. "La loi du 11 février 2005 pour l'égalité des droits et des chances, 20 ans après." *Handicap.gouv.fr*, 11 février 2025. <https://handicap.gouv.fr/la-loi-du-11-fevrier-2005-pour-legalite-des-droits-et-des-chances>.

Costil, Clotilde. "IA, handicap et emploi : le trio gagnant ?" *Handicap.fr*, 25 novembre 2023. <https://informations.handicap.fr/a-ia-handicap-et-emploi-le-trio-gagnant-35929.php>.

Beky, Ariane. "Emploi : l'intelligence artificielle manque de développeurs." *Silicon.fr*, 4 mai 2018. <https://www.silicon.fr/Thematique/actualites-1367/Breves/Emploi-l-intelligence-artificielle-manque-de-developpeurs-443043.htm>.

COMPLEX BIASES IN GENERATIVE AI: EXPLORING RELIGIOUS BIAS IN STABLE DIFFUSION

- Auerbach, C., & Silverstein, L. B. (2003). *Qualitative data: An introduction to coding and analysis* (Vol. 21). NYU press
- Bianchi, F., Kalluri, P., Durmus, E., Ladhak, F., Cheng, M., Nozza, D., Hashimoto, T., Jurafsky, D., Zou, J., and Caliskan, A. (2022). "Easily Accessible Text-to-Image Generation Amplifies Demographic Stereotypes at Large Scale". ArXiv preprint. Available at <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2211.03759.pdf>
- Biewald, L. [Weights & Biases] (2022, November 15). "Emad Mostaque — Stable Diffusion, Stability AI, and What's Next" [Video file]. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bG5hTokyh5Q&t=2s> [Last accessed 30/11/2022]
- Boulamwini, J., & Gebru, T. (2018). "Gender Shades: Intersectional Accuracy Disparities in Commercial Gender Classification". *Proceeds of machine Learning Research*, 81, 77-91.
- Cho, J., Zala, A., and Bansal, M. (2022). "DALL-Eval: Probing the Reasoning Skills and Social Biases of Text-to-Image Generative Transformers". ArXiv preprint, abs/2202.04053. Available at <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2202.04053.pdf>.
- Flek, L. (2020). "Returning the N to NLP: Towards contextually personalized classification models." Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics, 7828–7838. Online: *Association for Computational Linguistics*. <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.acl-main.700>
- Foong, N.W. (2022, August 31). "How to Fine-tune Stable Diffusion using Textual Inversion. towards data science". Retrieved from <https://towardsdatascience.com/how-to-fine-tune-stable-diffusion-using-textual-inversion-b995d7ecc095> [Last accessed 01/12/2022]
- Garg N., Schiebinger L., Jurafsky D., & Zou J., (2018). "Word embeddings quantify 100 years of gender and ethnic stereotypes". 2018 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(16), 3635-3644. <https://www.pnas.org/doi/full/10.1073/pnas.1720347115>
- Gonen, H., & Goldberg, Y. (2019). "Lipstick on a pig: Debiasing methods cover up systematic gender biases in word embeddings but do not remove them". Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: *Human Language Technologies, Volume 1* (Long and Short Papers), 609–614. <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/N19-1061>
- Hovy, D., & Prabhumoye, S. (2021). "Five sources of bias in natural language processing". *Language and Linguistics Compass*, e12432. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lnc3.12432>
- Hovy, D., & Yang, D. (2021). "The importance of modeling social factors of language: Theory and practice." Proceedings of the 2021 *Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies*, 588–602. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2021.naacl-main.49>
- Joshi, P., Santy, S., Budhiraja, A., Bali, K., & Choudhury, M. (2020). "The state and fate of linguistic diversity and inclusion in the NLP world". Proceedings of the 58th *Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 6282–6293. Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.acl-main.560>
- Kilcher, Y. (2022, August 13). "The Man behind Stable Diffusion" [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch>
- Kozlowski, A. C., Taddy, M., & Evans, J. A. (2019). "The geometry of culture: Analyzing the meanings of class through word embeddings". *American Sociological Review*, 84(5), 905-949.
- Labov, W. (1972). "Sociolinguistic patterns". Philadelphia, *University of Pennsylvania Press*. Mostaque, E. [@EMostaque] (2022, August 28). We actually used 256 A100s for this per the model card, 150k hours in total so at market price \$600k [Tweet]. Twitter. Retrieved from <https://twitter.com/EMostaque/status/1563870674111832066> [Last accessed 01/12/2022]

COMPLEX BIASES IN GENERATIVE AI: EXPLORING RELIGIOUS BIAS IN STABLE DIFFUSION

Quillian L, Pager D. "Estimating Risk: Stereotype Amplification and the Perceived Risk of Criminal Victimization". *Soc Psychol Q.* 2010 Mar 1;73(1):79-104. doi: 10.1177/0190272509360763. PMID: 20686631; PMCID: PMC2914342.

Sap, M., Card, D., Gabriel, S., Choi, Y., & Smith, N. A. (2019). "The risk of racial bias in hate speech detection". Proceedings of the 57th *Conference of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 1668–1678. Florence, Italy: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/P19-1163>

Skrodzka, M., Kende, A., Faragó, L. & Bilewicz, M. (2022). "Remember that we suffered!" The effects of historical trauma on anti-Semitic prejudice". *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 52, 341– 350. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jasp.12862>

Stability AI (2022a, November 24). "Stable Diffusion License Model". GitHub. Retrieved from <https://github.com/Stability-AI/stablediffusion/blob/main/LICENSE-MODEL> [Last accessed 30/11/2022]

Sutkutė, R. (2019). "Media, stereotypes and muslim representation: world after Jyllands-Posten Muhammad cartoons controversy". *EUREKA: Social and Humanities*, (6), 59-72. Stability AI (n.d.). "What was the Stable Diffusion Model trained on?" *Stable Diffusion FAQ*. Retrieved from <https://stability.ai/faq> [Last accessed 30/11/2022].

TheLastBen (2022). "Fast-stable-diffusion". Github. Retrieved from <https://github.com/TheLastBen/fast-stable-diffusion> [Last accessed 01/12/2022]

Yacben (2022, October 25). "New (simple) Dreambooth method is out, train under 10 minutes without class images on multiple subjects, retrainable-ish model" [Reddit post]. Retrieved from https://www.reddit.com/r/StableDiffusion/comments/yd9oks/new_simple_dreambooth_method_is_out_train_under/ [Last accessed 01/12/2022]

PART 3

BUILDING ACCOUNTABILITY : TRANSPARENCY, EXPLAINIBILITY AND APPEAL PROCESSES: THE CASE OF AMS AUSTRIA

Allhutter, Doris, Florian Cech, Fabian Fischer, Gabriel Grill, et Astrid Mager. "Algorithmic Profiling of Job Seekers in Austria: How Austerity Politics Are Made Effective." *Frontiers in Big Data* 3 (2020): Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdata.2020.00005>.

Ada Lovelace Institute, AI Now Institute, & Open Government Partnership. "Algorithmic Accountability for the Public Sector: Learning from the First Wave of Policy Implementation". 24 august 2021. <https://www.adalovelaceinstitute.org/report/algorithmic-accountability-public-sector/>.

Digital Regulation Cooperation Forum. "Auditing Algorithms: The Existing Landscape, Role of Regulators and Future Outlook." 23 septembre 2022. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/findings-from-the-drcf-algorithmic-processing-workstream-spring-2022/auditing-algorithms-the-existing-landscape-role-of-regulators-and-future-outlook>.

Koshiyama, Adriano, Emre Kazim, Philip Treleaven, Pete Rai, Lukasz Szpruch, Giles Pavey, Ghazi Ahamat, et al. "Towards Algorithm Auditing: A Survey on Managing Legal, Ethical and Technological Risks of AI, ML and Associated Algorithms." SSRN, 15 février 2021. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3778998>.

Public Employment Service Austria (AMS). "About the AMS." Mis à jour le 3 juin 2024. <https://www.ams.at/organisation/public-employment-service-austria/about-ams>.

AMS Algorithmus. "AMS Algorithmus." Consulté le 30 mai 2025. <https://amsalgorithmus.at/en/>.

Ziewitz, Malte. "Governing Algorithms: Myth, Mess, and Methods." *Social Studies of Science* 45, no. 1 (2016): 3–17. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444816676645>.

Universität Lausanne. "Référence bibliographique pour serval:BIB_83DBDEA5F696." Consulté le 30 mai 2025. https://serval.unil.ch/resource/serval:BIB_83DBDEA5F696.P001/REF.

ENSURING THE RIGHT EFFECTIVE REMEDIES IN WELFARE ADM: THE CASE OF THE DUTCH SYRI

- Brouwer, J. (2023). "Digital injustice: The social and legal failures of SyRI". *Utrecht Law Review*, 19(1), 34–52.
- Craig, P., & de Búrca, G. (2020). "EU Law: Text, Cases, and Materials" (7th ed.). *Oxford University Press*.
- ECJ Case C-806/24. (2024). *Judgment of the European Court of Justice on explainability and remedies in public ADM*.
- Eubanks, V. (2018). *Automating Inequality: How High-Tech Tools Profile, Police, and Punish the Poor*. St. Martin's Press.
- European Commission. (2022). *Proposal for a Directive on adapting non-contractual civil liability rules to artificial intelligence (AI Liability Directive)*. COM(2022) 496 final.
- GDPR Recital 71. (2016). *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data*.
- Huissen, J. (2021). "The SyRI Scandal and the Right to Contest Automated Decisions" [YouTube Video & Interview]. Bits of Freedom.
- Mantelero, A. (2022). "Beyond explainability: The role of transparency in contestability and meaningful human control". *Computer Law & Security Review*, 45, 105661.
- Van Schendel, K. (2022). "SyRI and the automation of suspicion: Data-driven welfare control in the Netherlands". *Journal of Law and Society*, 49(2), 235–255.
- Veale, M., & Brass, I. (2019). "Administration by algorithm? Public management meets public sector machine learning." *Public Money & Management*, 39(5), 321–326.
- Wachter, S., Mittelstadt, B., & Floridi, L. (2017). "Why a right to explanation of automated decision-making does not exist in the General Data Protection Regulation". *International Data Privacy Law*, 7(2), 76–99.

UNDERSTANDING PUBLIC OPINION ON AI IN POLICY-MAKING USING POL.IS

Deranty, J., Corbin, T. (2024). "Artificial intelligence and work: a critical review of recent research from the social sciences". *AI & Society*, 39, p. 675–691.

Howlett, M., Ramesh, M. (1995), "Studying Public Policy: Policy Cycles and Policy Subsystems", *Oxford University Press*.

Taeihagh, A. (2021). "Governance of artificial intelligence, Policy and Society", 40(2), p. 137–57.

Wang, Q., Li, Y. & Li, R. (2024). "Ecological footprints, carbon emissions, and energy transitions: the impact of artificial intelligence (AI)", *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11.

TIERED - SCIENCES PO STUDENT WORKS COLLECTION
Special IA Issue

Publishing Director: Marie-Hélène Caitucoli, TIERED Executive Director

Secretary general of the Open Institute for Digital Transformations: Carly Hafner

Layout : Lucile Chambon, TIERED Assistant

Graphic Conception : Studio Kali

SciencesPo
OPEN INSTITUTE FOR
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATIONS

SciencesPo

27, rue Saint-Guillaume 75007 Paris, France
www.sciencespo.fr
<https://www.sciencespo.fr/institut-libre-transformations-numeriques/en/>